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Challenges and Strategies in the Covid-19 Pandemic Education System

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ABSTRACT

In an attempt to halt the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, most governments throughout the world have temporarily closed educational institutions. These nationwide closures affect almost 90% of the world's school population and millions of more students. COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by a recently discovered corona virus. To get out of this bind, we should implement an open-source digital learning solution. Radio and television are also highly powerful tools, and social media platforms such as WhatsApp can successfully interact with parents and teachers while also providing guidance for the learning process. Teachers should map the E-learning settings and e-tools they utilize for distant learning in their schools during this pandemic. COVID-19 is also changing the educational system for our young students. In an interconnected world, we shall educate the learner. We should redefine the job of the educator and focus on teaching life skills that will be useful in the future. To deliver education, educational institutions should use technology. As education systems deal with the crisis, they must consider how to recover stronger, with a renewed sense of responsibility among all actors and a better understanding and sense of urgency about the need to close the opportunity gap and ensure that all children have equal access to a high-quality education.

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1. Introduction

First and foremost, the COVID-19 epidemic is a public health emergency. Many countries have made the decision to shut down schools, colleges, and institutions. Many families throughout the world are experiencing serious short-term disruptions as a result of home schooling: it is not just a tremendous shock to parents' productivity, but also to children's social lives and learning. On an unproven and unprecedented scale, education is migrating online. Student assessments are now migrating online, resulting in a lot of trial and error and uncertainty for all involved. Importantly, these disruptions will not be a one-time issue; they will likely have long-term effects for the afflicted cohorts and will likely increase inequality.

The first to be impacted by these closures was the organization of education and learning, including teaching and evaluation procedures. Only a few private schools are able to use online teaching methods. On the other hand, their low-income private and public-school rivals have totally shut down due to a lack of access to e-learning alternatives. In addition to missing out on learning opportunities, the pupils no longer have access to healthy meals during this time and are experiencing economic and social stress. The impact of COVID 19 on education is that attending to school is the most effective public policy tool for improving skills.

While education can be enjoyable and can improve social skills and awareness, the fundamental economic benefit of being in school is that it boosts a child's ability. Even a brief absence from school has an impact on skill development. Can we, however, predict how much the COVID-19 disruption will affect learning? We can't be accurate because we're in a new realm, but we can gain an order of magnitude from other studies.

2. Covid-19's Effect on the Education System

The corona virus pandemic of 2019–20 affected educational systems worldwide, resulting in the near-complete closure of schools, colleges, and universities. Due to school closures in response to the pandemic, approximately 1.723 billion students have been

impacted. According to UNESCO monitoring, 189 countries have implemented nationwide closures, with 5 implementing local closures, affecting approximately 98.4 percent of the world's student population. School closures have far-reaching economic and societal consequences, affecting not only students, teachers, and families. For underprivileged children and their families, the effects were more severe, producing disruptions in schooling, poor nutrition, childcare issues, and a financial cost to families who were unable to work. In reaction to school closures, UNESCO suggested that schools and teachers employ distance learning programs as well as open educational tools and platforms to reach learners remotely and minimize disruption of education.

The majority of the information gathered on the number of students and learners affected by COVID-19 was based on the shutdown of formal education systems. COVID-19 has an impact on pupils at all stages of education, including pre-primary, primary, lower-secondary, and upper-secondary education, as well as higher education, according to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics.

Families have an important role in education and are universally acknowledged as essential contributors to a child's learning. At first glance, the current global spread of home schooling may appear to be rather positive, as if it is going to be effective. However, this function is usually viewed as a supplement to the school's input. Being the primary driver of learning, even when using online materials, is a separate question; and while many parents around the world effectively homeschool their children, this does not appear to be true for the entire population.

3. Corona Virus Covid-19 Pandemic Educational Challenges and Opportunities

We are in the midst of a massive educational crisis, which could be one of the greatest challenges to world education in our lifetime. The COVID-19 pandemic has forced over 1.6 billion children and youth out of school in 161 nations as of March 28, 2020. We were already in the midst of a worldwide learning crisis, with many pupils attending school but

failing to gain the core skills required for success in life.

What should we be concerned about in this stage of the crisis that could have a direct impact on children and youth? (1) Learning losses (2) Dropout rates (3) Children missing their most critical meal of the day. Furthermore, most countries have extremely uneven educational systems, and impoverished children will bear the brunt of these detrimental consequences. It pours for them when it rains.

Learning- Many students, their parents, and instructors' lives are dramatically disrupted when the school year begins late or is interrupted. Through remote learning tactics, a lot may be done to at least mitigate the damage. The situation in middle-income and lower-income countries is very mixed, and if we do not act, the massive imbalance of opportunity that now exists – which is atrocious and immoral – will be exacerbated. Many youngsters do not have access to a desk, books, internet access, a laptop at home, or parents who are supportive. Others have done so. What we must avoid – or at least as much as possible – is for those disparities in opportunity to widen, causing the crisis to have an even greater detrimental impact on the learning of impoverished children.

Radio and television are also highly effective tools. The advantage we have now is that ministries of education may connect effectively with parents and instructors via social media, What's App, or SMS, using content given via radio or television, and provide directions, instructions, and structure to the learning process. Remote learning encompasses not only online but also mixed media learning, with the goal of reaching as many students as possible in today's world.

Maintaining children's engagement is referred to as "staying engaged" Many countries still have significant dropout rates, and a long period of disengagement can lead to an increase. Going to school is about more than just learning math and science; it's also about forming social bonds and interacting with peers. It's all about becoming a citizen and honing social skills. That is why it is critical to maintain contact with the school in every way possible. This is also an opportunity for all kids to

improve their socio-emotional abilities and learn more about how to contribute to society as a citizen.

4. Pandemic Covid-19 Educational Strategy

To manage the crisis and build a resilient Indian education system in the long run, a multi-pronged strategy is required. One, immediate measures are required to ensure learning continuity in government schools and Universities. Teachers should use open-source digital learning solutions and Learning Management Software to conduct online instruction. The DIKSHA (Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing) platform, which has a reach across all Indian states, can be strengthened further to ensure students' access to learning. Two, inclusive learning solutions, particularly for the most vulnerable and marginalized, are required. With a rapid increase in mobile internet users in India, which is expected to reach 85 percent of households by 2024, technology is enabling ubiquitous access and personalization of education even in the country's most remote areas. This has the potential to transform the educational system and improve the effectiveness of learning and teaching by providing students and teachers with a variety of options. Three, measures are needed to prepare the higher education system for changing demand–supply trends around the world, particularly those connected to global student and faculty mobility, as well as boosting the quality of and demand for higher education. Four, it's critical to rethink present delivery and pedagogical approaches in schools and higher education by smoothly merging classroom learning with e-learning modalities to create a single learning system. The seamless integration of technology in the current education system, which is the most diverse and largest in the world with over 15 million schools and 50,000 higher education institutions, is the key issue in ED Tech changes at the national level. Furthermore, quality assurance systems and quality benchmarks for online learning developed and delivered by Indian higher education institutions as well as e-learning platforms must be established (growing rapidly). Many e-learning providers provide multiple courses on the same subject with varying degrees of certificates, methodologies, and assessment criteria.

5. How does the corona virus affect our generation's education?

The COVID-19 dilemma has the potential to impact our world and our global outlook; it also has the potential to teach us about how education needs to evolve in order to better prepare our young learners for the future. The following are some of the lessons:

Citizenship education in an interconnected world:

COVID-19 is a pandemic that demonstrates how globally interconnected we are. Isolated situations and acts no longer exist. In the future decades, successful people will need to be able to recognize this interconnectedness and traverse across boundaries to leverage their uniqueness and collaborate globally.

The educator's job is being redefined:

The idea of an educator as a knowledge-holder who teaches wisdom to students is no longer appropriate for a twenty-first-century education. We will need to reinvent the role of the educator in the classroom and lecture theatre as students may acquire access to knowledge and even learn a technical skill with a few clicks on their phones, tablets, and computers. This could indicate that educators' roles will shift to assisting young people's growth as contributing members of society.

Teaching future-oriented life skills:

Young people demand resilience and adaptability in this ever-changing global context, abilities that are proving to be critical in navigating this pandemic efficiently. Employers will be searching for creativity, communication, and collaboration in the future, as well as empathy and emotional intelligence; and the ability to collaborate across demographic lines to harness the collective potential through successful teamwork.

Unleashing the power of technology to offer education:

As a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, educational institutions all over the world have been

forced to immediately grasp and use the suite of accessible technological resources to develop content for remote learning for students from all sectors. Educators all over the world are discovering new ways to do things differently and with more flexibility, which could improve access to education for kids all over the world.

6. Conclusion

A well-rounded and successful educational practice is required for the capacity-building of young minds in this time of crisis. It will help them build skills that will improve their employability, productivity, health, and well-being in the coming decades, as well as overall progress.

Some countries will be able to improve the digital abilities of its instructors. Radio and television stations will realize their critical role in advancing national education goals – and, ideally, improve the quality of their programming as a result of their enormous social duty.

Every educational system has the same goal. It's about overcoming the learning crisis we've already been through and responding to the pandemic we're all dealing with. The task today is to minimize the negative impact of the epidemic on learning and schooling as much as possible, and to build on this experience to return to a path of faster learning improvement. As education systems deal with the crisis, they must consider how to recover stronger, with a renewed sense of responsibility among all actors and a better understanding and sense of urgency about the need to close the opportunity gap and ensure that all children have equal access to a high-quality education.

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